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Causes And Remedies Of Student Drop-Out In Secondary School In Yobe North Senatorial District , Yobe State Nigeria

Shuaibu Maidami¹; Yusuf Yerima²; Musa Haruna³ & Audu Ibrahim⁴

^{1,2}Department of Social Science and Humanity

Umar Suleiman College of Education Gashua, Yobe State, Nigeria

¹Phone No 08067678574-07088884210 Email shuaibungu@gmail.com

²08108089731 yusufyerima1144@gmail.com

³07037226845 musaharuna@gmail.com

⁴Department of Social Studies

Umar Suleiman College of Education Gashua, Yobe State, Nigeria

08132066518

ABSTRACT

The objective of this study is to examine the causes and effects of student drop-out in secondary school in Yobe north senatorial district, Yobe State. This study adopted survey research design. The data was collected from the sample of 120 respondents through questionnaire. The data collected was analyzed by the use of simple statistical table and percentage. The study reveals that the student drop-out in Yobe north senatorial district are as a result of indiscipline, poor academic performances, lack of guidance and counseling, socioeconomic background of the parents and lack of employment after graduation among others. The study also shows that drop-out of student from secondary school in Yobe north senatorial district is affecting the community because it shows that school drop-out brings about low literacy level in the community, increase in armed robbery, gangs provides hooligans, a political thug by politicians, produces social misfits and person who are never positively self-actualized. Based on the finding the study recommended that the school authority and parents should monitor the movement of students so as to prevent them from bad groups that results in indiscipline and The government should expand free and compulsory education by providing uniforms, text book and other learning materials to children at secondary school level.

.Keywords- Drop-out, Remedies, Secondary schools

INTRODUCTION

School dropout its simplest meaning is the untimely withdrawal from school. These students who withdraw from school prematurely end up not obtaining any certificate of graduation; the issue of school dropout is a global problem confronting the education industry round the world. Mohsin, et al, (2004), The issue of school dropout has been with us for a very long time, even before our independence the problem of dropout has already established it is grip on our educational system. This can be buttressed with the remark made Nuffied foundation in (1953) that in west cost of Africa, a considerable proportion of students drop out of school each year.

This study has come at a time when there is high rate of insecurity in the country as a result of criminal activities. Survey by book the print and electric media tends to indicate that over 55% of the criminal activities perpetuated in Nigerian are done by youths who dropped out of school. This development has become a cause of serious concern to all well-meaning Nigerian. This tends to suggest that our educational system is in trouble and thus needs a very serious attention in refocusing it and restructuring it for attainment of national goals. In Nigerian of today, senior school certificate is considered as minimum required for most Jobs and status positions, the development has serious implications for the economic well-being of drop-outs and the society at large, in this era of global economic meltdown and global economic competitiveness, Nigeria as a nation that has vision must make concerted efforts to raise the educational attainment of all its youths who are the leaders of tomorrow.

Globally reason why students dropout from school can be categorized in to four cluster, these include school related, job related, family related and community related, study by Frendenberg et-al (2007) identified twenty four factors under family cluster, three factors under community cluster, and twelve factors under school cluster. The factors identified under family cluster, low family socioeconomic status, racial or ethnic groups male special education status, low family supports for education, low parental education, residential mobility low social conformity, low acceptance of adult authority. Most of the researchers on the cause of dropout in Nigeria isolated the following (i) poor educational background of parents, (ii) in ability of parents to pay their children school fees, (iii) failure in school examination, (iv) very poor state of facilities in schools, (v) broken home, (vi) types of parents occupation (vii) School discipline policies, (viii) Teenage pregnancy, (ix) Early marriage and (x) Very early ambition for self-business and employment.

Statement of the problem

The cause of student dropout have continued to be prevalent in our society, there is hardly any term or session in which secondary school authorities do not record students drop out of school as a result of one factor or another. Poverty, lack awareness, peer group, early marriage,.

Problem caused by these drip-out student include rioting town, at of hooliganism, they are used as instrument of violence. On other hand, some of them become a professional robbers, there by caused profound problems to their community, this situation has captured the interest of the research and hence the need to research on causes and solution of student dropout of secondary.

Research questions

The following are research questions for the study.

- (a) What are the causes of student dropout?
- (b) What effect does it have on the society?
- (c) what are the possible solutions to students dropout from secondary schools in Yobe North Senatorial District?

Objectives of the study

The objectives are as follows;

- (i) To determine the causes of secondary school student dropout in Yobe north senatorial district.
- (ii) To determine the effect of dropout on society.
- (iii). To proffer solution to students dropout from secondary schools in Yobe North Senatorial District

Review of related literature.

Concept of student drop-out

A student who discontinued school before graduation is called school drop-out. Also is one who abandoned and understanding before completing it.

Farant (1981) defined student drop-out as those student who despite having the ability an educational course or failed to do so. The problem according to him was common in rural area where parents are not enlightened enough on the value of education; they therefore take them to farm or encourage them, to trade even at their tender age.

In summary drop-out are those person who leaves schools either voluntarily or by through lack of performance in academic work, being involve in antisocial act which made them to leave before the official stipulation time of completion. Literature on dropout six predictive factors for dropping out of high schools, these include (a) grade retention (being held back to repeat a grade) (b) poor academic performance (c) move during high school (d) high absenteeism (e) Misbehaviors and (f) the student feeling that no adult in the school vets about his or her welfare student with the above characteristics have very high tendency to drop-out of school.

Causes of students drop-out in Yobe north senatorial districts.

According to Obia (1982) in her study parent attitude towards western education in Yobe state north senatorial district, some withdrew their children from school at early age. They feel bit was a sources of disagreement when their daughter become pregnant illegally and paid some fund if found to be a virgin on the day of their marriage. They believe that the longer the girl stay at school the more she become sophisticated and the more her behaviours become contrary to the value of the society in which belongs, parents also believe that too much exposure of children to immoral acts changes their characters.

These believe if patents toward western education are contributing to female drop-out in secondary school level, in another study Alogbe (1971) attributed that female drop-out is caused by indiscipline in sch. Some girls with draw themselves from school voluntary while some do that due to their parents attitude towards western education, parents, says that when girls are educated they are expose to evils and vices of modern civilization and they become pregnant. However, indiscipline of some student lead to drop-out various types of indiscipline behaviour is manifested across all the segment of our school system that is primary, post primary etc.

Ojile (1995) mentioned many among indiscipline behaviours as follows:

- (1) Truancy lathering aimlessly.
- (2) Breaking rules and regulation in school.
- (3) Disregard for authority
- (4) Mis-use of the right of others, littering of the campuses compound with pieces of property.
- (5) Noise making without due regard for other.
- (6) Malpractice in examination of various Kinds.

The result of indiscipline is the rise in violence and subsequent closure of the school thus contributing academic programme. With such scenario the realization of educational objectives become a mirage and mere dream, his did our school degenerate to such an abysmal state, there are many factors responsible for the problem some of these factors include parental negligence to improve discipline in children from home.

One (1985) opined that 'parent' in Nigerian believe to be contributors to student unrest some parent are neither discipline nor morally upright. Some even go to the extent of interfering with the discipline of their children by confronting teacher who has disciplined their children.

- (1) The modern family life style does not sphere the time to children's moral development.
- (2) Influence of the permissive western culture through the mass media most home today are privilege to own either a radio or television with video player or both. Some children are exposed to print media with sketch of violent action. Children learn by watching how people behave, whether role models are seen like on a television make little or no difference causes it will have on the child.
- (3) Lack of recreation facilities or non-functioning of the facilities according to Jocham (1996) in adequate games equipment will bread unhealthy mind.

This is seen both within and outside classroom activities, where communication between teachers and students widens, student may likely wrong decision which may border on indiscipline nonfunctional guidance and counseling, most of our schools lack counselors, where they exist they are not being properly used, some of the major function of the school environment and their community by behaving in socially accepted manner. They also help the student to understand themselves. The absence of these

cause unresolved conflict within the student, to make him/her to behave in unacceptable manner which is indiscipline.

Some indiscipline behaviour of student contributed to their drop-out in school, the in disciplinary behaviour of student need to be checked to minimize the cause of drop-out.

Lawini (1997) also buttressed that discipline could checked by introduction of group work, group play, drama and peer teaching by their role as foundation agent of socialization.

Adma S. Noma (1967) identify the factors causing student drop-out to include lack of recognition of the link between what is through and the need for future life, arrogant and bad tempered of teachers and poor quality of the school themselves. Other factors he pointed include, poor homes of the student, location of the school, chronic diseases, malnutrition and prejudice against western education, in his discussion of current policy Thomas (1968) said financial pressure and lack off counselling and guidance services in the school are causes of student drop-out. Another point which he identified is poor quality of instruction in public schools.

According to Badah (1996) is characterized by:-

- 1) Applicability only to an individual.
- 2) It is compensability to qualification percentage or other numerical indices.
- 3) It is susceptibility to various failure in retaining it in short term and long term through influence

responsibility of the carry over effect and the maturation effect.

Fafunwa (1986) opined that the problem of drop-out exist in our facilities and equipment in another view he said that student drop-out of school archives, that is perform every well, perform itself if is to carry out in action execute, do to perform in accordance with his requirement or obligation to fulfil, discharge as a duty or command, so far a child to perform every well in academic, he need support from the family, the family has an important in other word which help in his day to day life.

Ben (1985) affirmed that one major problem hindering school from achieving its objective is the high rate of drop-out among lower social class for the following reasons:-

- 1) Lower class students cannot afford to maintain peer standard in dresses, so they are unable to gain peer approval.
- 2) Early marriage, economic necessity and unwanted pregnancies are some of the contributing factors to school drop-out.
- 3) Religion is also the factors that are responsible for females school drop-out.

Oloyinka (1976) conducted an investigation entitled wastage of human resources, the case of school drop-out in Yobe north senatorial district the purpose of the study was to determine the peculiar characteristic of families with drop-out, such as parent occupation, size of family, and the education status of the parents.

His result revealed that the fathers of the drop-out are mostly farmers with 50% while their mothers are mostly Petty traders with 77%.

Solution to student drop-out

According to Wikipedia Dictionary- Solution could be define as a means of solving problem or dealing with a difficult situation. Therefore the solution to student drop-out could be discuss as follows:

- 1) Mentoring/Tutoring is a one to one caring, supportive relationship between a mentor that is based on trust. Tutoring also a one to one activity, focuses on academic and is an effective way to address specific needs such as reading, writing or Match competencies.
- 2) Service learning: service learning connect meaningful community services experiences with academic, this teaching and learning method promotes personal and social growth, career development and civic responsibility and can be a powerful vehicle for effective school reform at all grade levels.
- 3) Alternative schooling: alternative schooling provides potential drop-out a variety of opinions that can lead to graduation, with programmes paying special attention to the student individual social needs and the academic requirement for a secondary school.

4) After school opportunities: many schools provide after-school and summer enhancement programs that eliminate information loss and inspire interest in a variety of area. Such experiences are especially important for students at risk of school failure.

5) Family engagement: Researches consistently find that family involvement has a direct positive effect on children's achievement and is the most accurate predictor of student success in school.

METHODOLOGY

The study used primary source of data. Primary source of data is the firsthand information which research collected directly from respondents; therefore, this study uses questionnaire. Data were collected through a questionnaire distributed to the sampled population of 120 respondents in four sample schools in four local government areas in the senatorial zone. Data collected through questionnaire was analyzed using frequency table and simple percentage.

PRESENTATION OF DATA

The data collected in an investigation into cause and solution of students drop-out in some secondary school in Yobe north senatorial district, the data collected is presented bellows.

Table 1: indiscipline is one of the causes of students drop-out in secondary schools.

Variable	Frequency	Percentage
Agreed	100	83.3
Disagreed	20	16.7
Total	120	100

Source: Field survey, 2026

The above table shows that (83.3%) of the respondents agree that indiscipline is one of the causes of students drop-out in secondary schools while (16.7%) disagreed with the statement.

Table 2: Poor academic performance is another cause of students drop-out in Yobe North Senatorial District.

Variable	Frequency	Percentage
Agreed	80	66.7
Disagreed	40	33.3
Total	120	100

Source: Field survey, 2026

The above table shows that (66.7%) of the respondents agreed that Poor academic performance is one of another causes of students drop-out, while (33.3%) of the respondent disagreed.

Table 3: Lack of guidance and counseling in the school leads to drop-out in Yobe North Senatorial District.

Variable	Frequency	Percentage
Agreed	70	58.3
Disagreed	50	41.7
Total	120	100

Source: Field survey, 2026

The above table shows that (50.3%) of the respondents agreed that lack of guidance and counseling in school lead to student drop-out in secondary school. While (41.7 %) of the respondents disagreed with the statement.

Table 4: Socio-economic background of parents leads to drop-out in schools in Yobe North Senatorial District.

Variable	Frequency	Percentage
Agreed	60	50
Disagreed	60	50
Total	120	100

Source: Field survey, 2026

The table above shows that (50%) of the respondent agreed that Socio-economic background of parents leads to drop-out in schools. While the same percentage disagreed with statement.

Table 5: School environment factor lead to students drop-out in secondary schools in Yobe North Senatorial District.

Variable	Frequency	Percentage
Agreed	60	50
Disagreed	60	50
Total	120	100

Source: Field survey, 2026

The above table show that (50%) of the respondents agreed that School environment factor lead to students drop-out in secondary schools. While the same number as above disagreed with the statement.

Table 6: Lack of employment after graduation from secondary school leads to the drop-out in school in Yobe North Senatorial District.

Variable	Frequency	Percentage
Agreed	70	58.3%
Disagreed	50	41.7
Total	120	100

Source: Field survey, 2026

The above table shows that (58.3%) of the respondents agreed that lack of employment after graduation from secondary school leads to the drop-out in school. While (41.7%) disagreed with the statement.

Table 7: Students drop-out in school causes lack of literacy progress in Yobe North Senatorial District.

Variable	Frequency	Percentage
Agreed	110	91.7
Disagreed	10	8.3
Total	120	100

Source: Field survey, 2026

The above table shows that (91.7%) of the respondents agreed that students drop-out in school causes lack of literacy progress in the society. While (8.3%) disagreed with the statement.

Table 8: School drop-out in society brings about increased in armed robbery Gangs, kidnapping in Yobe North Senatorial District.

Variable	Frequency	Percentage
Agreed	80	66.7
Disagreed	40	33.3
Total	120	100

Source: Field survey, 2026

The above table shows that (66.7%) of the respondent agreed that School drop-out in society brings about increased in armed robbery Gangs, kidnapping. While (33.3%) disagreed the statement.

Table 9: School drop-out causes the cost of proper placement of people in to carrier of Job within the society.

Variable	Frequency	Percentage
Agreed	75	62.5
Disagreed	45	37.5
Total	120	100

Source: Field survey, 2026

The above table shows that {62.5%} of the respondents agreed that School drop-out causes the cost of proper placement of people in to carrier of Job within the society. While (37.5%) disagreed the statement.

Table 10: School drop-out lead to high risk of behavior in Yobe North Senatorial District

Variable	Frequency	Percentage
Agreed	70	58.3
Disagreed	50	41.7
Total	120	100

Source: Field survey, 2026

The above table shows that (58.3%) of the respondents agreed that School drop-out lead to high risk of behavious. While (50.41%) disagreed with the statement.

Table 11: School drop-out lead to psychopathic behaviours in Yobe North Senatorial District.

Variable	Frequency	Percentage
Agreed	60	50
Disagreed	60	50
Total	120	100

Source: Field survey, 2026

The above table shows that equal number of the respondent are on the agreeing and disagreeing side respectively (50%) of the respondent agreed that school drop-out lead to psychopathic behaviours. While the same percentage disagreed with the statement.

Table 12: School drop-out mostly never positively self-actualized in Yobe North Senatorial District.

Variable	Frequency	Percentage
Agreed	80	65.2
Disagreed	40	34.8
Total	120	100

Source: Field survey, 2026

The above table shows that (65.2%) of the respondent agreed that School drop-out mostly never positively self actualized. While (34.8%) disagreed with the statement.

Table 13: Hooligans are person usually used as thugs and fermenting crises community are mostly are drop-out.

Variable	Frequency	Percentage
Agreed	75	60.3
Disagreed	45	39.8
Total	120	100

Source: Field survey, 2026

The above table shows that (60.3%) of the respondent agreed that Hooligans are person usually used as thugs and fermenting crises community are mostly are drop-out. While (39.8%) disagreed with the statement.

Table 14: As a result school drop-out the castellan centre is increasing in Yobe North Senatorial District.

Variable	Frequency	Percentage
Agreed	90	75.5
Disagreed	30	24.5
Total	120	100

Source: Field survey, 2026

The above table shows that (75.5%) of the respondents agreed that As a result school drop-out the castellan center are increase in the society. While (24.5%) disagreed with the statement.

Table 15: Remedies to dropout of schools in Yobe North Senatorial District

Items	Agree	%	Disagree	%	Total
Provision of free or subsidized education	65	54.2	55	45.8	120(100%)
School meal programme	72	60.0	48	40.0	120(100%)
Cash transfer programme	88	73.3	32	26.7	120(100%)
Provision of learning materials and uniforms	97	80.8	23	19.2	120(100%)
Community awareness and advocacy programme	101	84.2	19	15.8	120(100%)

Source: Author's Computation 2026

Table 15 above revealed that 54.2% of the respondents agreed that Provision of free or subsidized education can be a solution to out of school children while 45.8% disagree. 60% of the respondents agreed that School meal programme is a solution to out of school children while 40% disagree. The table further revealed that 73.3% of the respondents agreed that Cash transfer programme remedy out of school children while 26.7% disagree. 80.8% of the respondents are of the view that Provision of learning materials and uniforms is a solution to out of school children in the study area while 19.2% disagree and 84.2% of the respondents agreed that Community awareness and advocacy programme proffer solution to out of school children.

FINDING

The study revealed that indiscipline among students, lack of proper guidance and counseling and socioeconomic factors including poverty and unemployment within households are the direct cause of student drop-out from school in the study area.

There are also very high level of robbery assassination and kidnapping associated with youths most of whom are school drop-out, in fact Nigerian is today most insecure because of criminal youths activities, this insinuation agrees with the position held by both the electric and print media from a survey that 85% of criminal activities perpetuated in Nigeria are done by youths who dropped out of school.

Solution to dropout of school as revealed by the analyses of the data include Provision of free or subsidized education, School meal programme, Cash transfer programme, Provision of learning materials and uniforms, and Community awareness and advocacy programme.

CONCLUSION

The study concluded that the student drop-out in Yobe north senatorial district are as a result of indiscipline, poor academic performances, lack of guidance and counseling, socioeconomic background if the parents, drug abuse and cultism, lack of employment after graduation among others are the causes of student drop-out in the study area. The study also shows that drop-out of student from secondary school in Yobe north senatorial district is affecting the community because it shows that school drop-out brings

about low literacy level in the community. increase in armed robbery, gangs provides hooligans, a political thug by politicians, produces social misfits and person who are never positively self-actualized.

RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the finding of this study the following are recommendation made by the researcher on how to stop or minimized student drop-out among the student of secondary school in Yobe north senatorial district.

- 1- Both the school authority and parents should monitor the movement of students so as to prevent them from bad groups that results in indiscipline.
- 2- The government should expand free and compulsory education by providing uniforms, text book and other learning materials to children at secondary school level.
- 3- Guidance and counseling should be established in most of the secondary schools with professional workers employed by government to help the student to enhance their endowment area of study.
- 4- The government should create more employment and poverty alleviation programmes for parents since improved household income will increase the ability of families to send their children to schools.

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